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DELIVERABLE 8.2

Dissemination & Exploitation plan 2

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List of Acronyms

ASRM	American Society of Reproductive Medicine	GRL	Wellcome Sanger Institute	IP	Intellectual property
BAHIA	Bahia Software, SL.	H2020	Horizon 2020	IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
CA	Consortium Agreement	HCA	Human Cell Atlas	KPI	Key performance indicator
C&D	Communication and Dissemination	HCA-DCP	Human Cell Atlas Data Coordination Platform	R&D	Research and development
C&D-M	Communication and dissemination Manager	HPA	Human Protein Atlas	RNA	Ribonucleic Acid
CCHT	Competence Centre on Health Technologies	HUTER	Human Uterus Cell Atlas Project	SME	Small and Medium enterprise
EC	European Commission	IAB	Industry Advisory Board	UPPSALA	Uppsala University
EMBL-EBI	European Bioinformatic institute of the European Molecular Biology Laboratory	IC	Innovation Committee	UEA	University of East Anglia
ESHRE	European Society of Human Reproduction	ICT	Information and Communication Technologies	WP	Work Package
EU	European Union	IM	Innovation Manager	INCLIVA	Fundación para la Investigación del Hospital Clínico de la Comunidad Valenciana
GA	Grant Agreement				

Purpose of this document

The purpose of this report is to present an update on the Plan for the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of the HUTER's project results. It aims to draw an overview of the actions and procedures that the HUTER consortium is following until the project ends.

As highlighted on the Fact sheet of the IPR Helpdesk about the plan for the exploitation and dissemination of the results, this is a strategic document in which the consortium partners defined the bases for the management of the results and provides information on the actions that are being taken. This deliverable is a

continuation of deliverable D8.1_*Dissemination & Exploitation Plan 1* (submitted in month 3) and adapts the strategy to the new events that have arisen or may arise during the project development. It is a very similar document to deliverable D8.1 following same structure but latest advancements are provided.

This document has been developed by INCLIVA as lead of the Work package 8 (WP8): Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan, in close collaboration with BAHIA partner. Then, it is shared to the rest of the partners for the revision and comments, so all members of the consortium are aware about the processes and procedures.

Related documents:

D8.1_Dissemination & Exploitation Plan 1

D8.3_HUTER workshop

D8.4_Record on the Dissemination & Exploitation

D9.2_Data Management Plan

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

HUTER project is aimed to create the reference cellular map of the human uterus, being involved in the international Human Cell Atlas (HCA) initiative. HUTER consortium is committed to performing communication, dissemination and exploitation activities as described in WP8 and stated in the Grant Agreement signed. Main topics covered in this document are the basic communication, dissemination and exploitation concepts and its key messages and strategies established in the HUTER project. The document is divided in two main sections: 1. Communication and dissemination (C&D) plan, and 2. Exploitation plan. This deliverable is a continuation of deliverable D8.1.

For the communication and dissemination plan, the main objective, target audience and key messages will be commented slightly as were define at the start of the project and reported on deliverable D8.1. It describes the tools and channels already created or planned (toolkit1), as well as other already existing channels used for achieving our communication and dissemination objectives. Responsibilities and procedures are also commented on. Finally, how we are going to evaluate and report the achievements in this area are written. In the last section 2, it is outlined an “Initial Exploitation Plan” that primarily approach the exploitation objectives and strategy for the HUTER project that will be enforced during the project lifetime. The exploitation plan is defined how the results (any tangible or intangible output) are going to be available for partners owns, scientific, social or economic purposes. It is established as well how to evaluate them as protectable or not, and which will be the best strategy to follow. The Innovation Committee (IC) oversees the exploitation tasks and assists the Steering Committee (SC) when taken decisions related to intellectual property rights (IPR) and exploitation, as defined in section 2.3.1 (Innovation Committee)

1. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

We summarize the main differences between communication and dissemination as:

- **Communication** is about project and its results. It shows the impact and benefits and it is targeted to multiple audiences, including media and society. Websites and social media are some examples of communication tools.
- **Dissemination** is about results only; it describes and ensures results are available for others to use; it aims to transfer knowledge and results to audiences with an interest in the potential use, such as the scientific community, industry or policy makers. Some examples are peer-reviewed papers, books and book chapters, presentations on scientific conferences and social events.

It should be mentioned that communication and dissemination (C&D) actions can sometimes overlap.

1.1 C&D objectives and strategy

Our main objective continues on increasing the **visibility** of the HUTER project, its achievements and outputs, on selected communities and target groups within the European and International level. The collaboration with the HCA initiative will additionally facilitate to maximize such visibility as well as the expected impact in a wider population.

The specific objectives, as at the start of the project, in our C&D plan continue being:

1. To **raise awareness** about the Human Cell Atlas initiative and more specifically about HUTER project, its expected results and progress using effective communication means and tools.
2. To **create efficient communication among project partners** and **exchange experience** with other international HCA projects and above all with the six European Atlas Projects working in the field in order to join efforts, minimize duplications and maximize potential.
3. To **engage** external key scientists and innovators (industry representatives) mainly from Europe, in order to **increase European competitiveness in the field**.
4. To **disseminate** the fundamental knowledge, the methodologies (protocols) and technologies (HUTER platform) developed during the project in order **to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximizing the impact of HUTER project**.
5. To spread the **project results and achievements** among general public and policymakers aiming to **influence future research** in human reproduction and women's health fields.

To achieve these objectives, we are following the strategy based on the EC Guidelines for effective dissemination:

- An effective network with the other 6 European Atlas projects and the HCA initiative: attend meetings and relevant events, and joint efforts in C&D activities will maximise their impact.
- All research results/reports will be duly **reviewed**, and a copy will be sent to all partners involved in the project before these are published or disseminated. When appropriate, the reports will refer to other research projects and build on the existing results and literature.
- Research will be conducted following sound analysis and scientific practice **principles**, taking into account as much as possible policy requirements and needs.
- All partners who will contribute to the project activities will be **duly informed** about the final outcomes and the implications stemming from project results.
- All public results will be **accessible** from the project website and usable from all parties and collaborators who may benefit from them. The definition of the dissemination strategy is based on the identification of the following milestones: a) the subject of dissemination (what will be

disseminated), b) the identification of target audience (who will most benefit from the project results and who would be interested in learning about the project findings, c) the timing (when dissemination will take place), d) the dissemination management and policy (who is responsible of and how dissemination is ruled).

1.2 Timeline

The C&D objectives timeline is describe in Figure 1 and follow the HUTER GANNT and its main milestones. Some dissemination activities have taken place during the first 12 months of the project, although the most significant dissemination activities will be performed during the last 6 months when research results will be available.

Figure 1. Phases of the C&D plan for HUTER project. Milestones of the HUTER project are: M1-started tissue procurement, M2-HUTER platform architecture designed, M3-HUTER raw data available and HUTER platform architecture finalised, M4-Recruitment of research participants and donors finalised, M5-finalised the high resolution spatial maps and epigenomics maps, finalised visualization tools.

1.3 Targeted audiences

1.3.1 Internal

An effective internal C&D among the Consortium partners implies a key success element within the HUTER Project. It is assisting in the achievement of the C&D objectives. Bear in mind that they are also potential end-users of project results themselves.

Consortium’s support network is also relevant since they represent relevant experts in the main areas of the project and are members of associations, initiatives or organizations in the field, such as the HCA, the Human Protein Atlas (HPA), European Society of Human Reproduction (ESHRE), the American Society of Reproductive Medicine (ASRM), etc. Thus, HUTER partners play an important role in communicating to the scientific community and should therefore exploit opportunities to present the project and its results.

1.3.2 Collaborators: Human Cell Atlas initiative and European Atlas Projects

As described in Work package 1, HUTER consortium is committed to network with the HCA and the 6 other European Atlas Projects that address the creation of cell atlas in other key human organs. Also, GA at Article 42 establishes the *obligation to conclude a “written collaboration” agreement to coordinate the work (create and participate in common boards and advisory structures to decide on collaboration and synchronization of activities, including on management of outcomes, common approaches towards standardization...and commonly shared dissemination and awareness raising activities.*

The collaboration with the other six European projects funded by the Pilot Actions Human Cell Atlas Initiative of the Horizon 2020 program started on September 2020, much later than expected, but since then, partners have worked on the draft agreement that is in process of signature at the time of the report and held a 1 life meeting (January 2020) and 1 virtual telco (September 2020) presenting their projects.

Other collaborations with relevant initiatives such as the HPA are foresee within HUTER project: for example, some high resolution images generated in this project could be disseminated in the HPA portal, in order to maximise its target audience. This will be performed on a later stage.

1.3.3. External

Target groups continue being the same and Table 1 addresses the different C&D actions.

Table 1. *The identified type of external audience and the motivation to include them as target group for the C&D activities of the HUTER project.*

Target group	Motivation
Academic, clinical and research community	This group targets all research communities interested in the Human Uterus Cell Atlas due its potential to provide comprehensive cellular references to scientist, from basic research of uterine biology to clinically relevant applications in uterus health and diseases. Scientific contributions of the project are particularly interesting for researchers/clinicians working in reproductive medicine, gynaecology, and obstetrics, as well as regenerative medicine in other fields, for their own research activities. Data and new knowledge generated in HUTER project have enormous potential to better understand women’s genotypic and phenotypic affecting several women’s diseases and/or efficacy of Assisted Reproductive Techniques.
Innovation community: SMEs and large enterprises	Industry could benefit in the mid-long term from curated data and the tools to facilitate their usability (technological platform) made accessible in HUTER, in many new clinical products and software tools (e.g. new software products using HUTER data to deliver developmental cellular modelling, cellular safety for new drugs studies, algorithms to predict new biomarkers, etc.). Furthermore, industrial sector in lab equipment and consumables for High resolution and single cell characterization can find in the HUTER and HCA project a highly visible framework for early adoption of their solutions, testing and validation of their innovations. Reaching this target group will be also relevant to leverage interest from private investors. We also identify in this target group the private foundations with founding programmes for biomedicine projects. Our objective is to increase awareness among philanthropic

	private funders in the reproductive medicine field since Europe is still lagging in offer this type of funds.
Patients and patients' organizations	Women of any age as gynecological patients, women of reproductive age as obstetrics and gynecology patients, and infertile patients are important as they will be main beneficiaries of the projects results, not immediately, but in the near future. Besides that, it is important that the message arrive clearly to this audience, and they could be an instrument to transmit the relevance and necessity of this research. As an example, we will first direct our communication efforts to Fertility Europe (http://www.fertilityeurope.eu/) as it is an european umbrella organization that represents patient associations in the field of (in)fertility in more than 20 european countries.
General public and students	Students from all levels and general public.
Government bodies and policy makers	This is a wide group encompassing health local, regional authorities, representatives and associations, Ministries, parliaments, and Public Administrations at national and international level. There are several significant goals that can be promoted. For instance: the women's health prevention by information or early prevention detection by genomics screenings; the promotion of national funding schemes to support reproductive medicine or HCA initiative.

1.4 Key messages

On all our communications the general messages defined at the start of the project are launched depending on the audience:

1. HUTER project itself: general scope, aims, concept and milestones and plans to reach them.

- ✓ *The Human Uterus Cell Atlas (HUTER) project is aimed to create the reference map of the human uterus, as a crucial resource for the scientific community to define the cellular basis of health and disease, allowing the uterus healthcare, the rapid development of new diagnosis and prognosis tools and therapeutic advancements.*
- ✓ *HUTER will use advanced characterisation methodologies based on some of the latest technological advancements in single cell resolution measurements, together with the use of advanced data integration and analysis proprietary methodologies by our world-class partners.*
- ✓ *HUTER project will lay the groundwork for enabling improvements towards more personalised therapies and highly precise and less invasive diagnosis procedures.*

2. Scientific results: reached objectives and achievements:

- ✓ *HUTER project aims to derive single-cell and spatial maps of the healthy female uterus across the whole lifespan. These maps will provide an unprecedented insight into the location and identity of cells in developing endometrial and myometrial tissues, the remodelling of these*

tissues during the menstrual cycle in adult donors and transcriptional, morphological and genomics changes during ageing.

- ✓ HUTER will make available to the international research community on biomedicine, the first atlas of the human uterus, including:
 - Datasets on single-cell RNA sequencing and single-cell methylation and transcriptome
 - High resolution images of cells analysed in their histological context
 - Generated knowledge on new cell types and states, their spatial localization in tissues

3. Protocols and technological platform (in respect of IPR issues)

- HUTER is aligned with the HCA guidelines, standards and protocols for: Data platform, sampling approach, level of single-cell resolution, characterisation approaches.

4. Sustainability assessment results

- ✓ This project will deliver a platform design that promotes its usability (user interfaces, guidelines, use cases) and ensures its scalability.
- ✓ The Human Uterus Cell Atlas will be applied to a use case to demonstrate its potency as a discovery tool: the early diagnosis of preeclampsia, the disease with the highest incidence during pregnancy.

1.5 Actions and tools

All partners have contributed to that effort and will do their utmost to maximize the use of the defined dissemination tools and channels. In Table 2 is shown the C&D activities planned and their analysis of: Why – the purpose of the action, channel or tools; What will be communicated – the message; To whom – the audience; How – the method; When – the timing. It is also mentioned some main indicators for the evaluation of their progress. The key performance indicators (KPIs) will be considered more fully at section 1.7.2.

Table 2. Main C&D activities and why, to whom, what, when analysis and main indicators for their evaluation.

How (Method)	Why (objectives)	To whom (target audience)	What (key message)	When	Evaluation	Achievements first 12 months
HUTER Brand guideline and templates	to create and maintain a consistent and recognisable visual identity	All audiences	1, 2, 3, 4, 5.	Already launched at month 1. Ongoing throughout project and post-project	Usage logs and templates	Used by all partners
Website and joint landing page for Atlas projects	Awareness, Inform, Engage, Promote	All audiences	1, 2, 4	Already launched at month 2. Ongoing throughout project and post-project	Number of visits	See Annex VIII Google Analytics Annual report 2020

						HUTER Website connected with HCA DCP Website 5107 visits to HUTER Website
Social networks	Awareness, Inform, Engage, Promote	All audiences	All	Launched at month 5. Ongoing throughout project and post-project	Number of followers	Twitter Followers: 40 LinkedIn Followers: 91
Press Releases	Awareness	General public	1, 5	At the beginning and at the end of the project.	No. of media that have published the press releases	1 Press released launched with 17 press coverage
Brochure and video	Awareness	All external	1, 2	Available from month 5 or 6.	No. of copies distributed. No. of visualizations on YouTube	In process, to be approved by SC members
Industry consultations (HUTER questionnaire)	To engage external key scientists and innovators	External: Innovation community.	1, 3, 4	To be first launched at month 5 or 6.	No. of completed questionnaires collected	8 (Individual Advisory Board Members)
Reports and other project documents	communicate and disseminate HUTER project and its results	All audiences	All	Upon completion, according to the deliverables list	No. of downloads	To be perform in second year of the project when results achieved. Future action
Workshop and case studies	disseminate HUTER project and its results	External: academic, clinical and innovation community	3, 4	Scheduled at month 22.	No. of attendees	To be perform in second year of the project when results achieved. Future action
Attend HCA/ EC-H2020 Consortia (Atlas Projects)	To ensure coherence and communication between both HCA and projects funded under this topic	Collaborators	2, 3, 4	Throughout the project period	No. of attended meetings	2 (Meeting in Brussels Jan 2020 and Virtual Telco in Sep 2020)

Industry Advisory Board (IAB)	To engage	External: Innovation community.	3, 4	Throughout the project period	No. of people participating	8 as planned
Conferences Presentations /posters	To disseminate project results	External: academic, clinical and innovation community	3, 4	throughout the project period*, but expected mainly during last 6 months when results will be available	No. of attended conferences and kind of participation	5
Per-review articles in open access	To disseminate project results	Research community	1, 2, 3, 4	Scientific Journals (open access)	No. of citations	Estonia partner pending publication in 2021
Participation in key policy makers forums	Awareness	polycymakers	1, 4	Throughout the project period*,	At least 1 per year At least 1 per partner	Event with the Health Regional Authority from the Valencia Region

*Due the outbreak COVID-19 (caused by new coronavirus SARS-CoV-2), that was declared as pandemic by the WHO on March 11, 2020, conferences and meeting and all kind of face-to-face events worldwide in any field have been cancelled.

1.5.1 HUTER C&D Toolkit 1

LOGOS AND TEMPLATES:

The corporate style (logos and standard templates) has been used and maintain a consistent and recognisable visual identity of the project (Fig. 2). Templates are used in PowerPoint presentations and Word documents (an example are de format of the deliverables handed in to the EC). Partners are informed about the need to use the logo, colours of the HUTER visual identity guide (see Annex I) and templates (see Annex II) developed in the framework of the WP8 for all C&D internal and external activities.

Figure 2. HUTER logo

Partners must also make use of the EU emblem and the accompanying text (Fig. 3), in all internal and external communication and dissemination materials:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 874867.

Figure 3. EU logo and accompanying text to be used in internal and external communication and dissemination materials.

PROJECT WEBSITE:

The HUTER official website (<https://huter-hca.eu/>) has become core in the digital communication and dissemination activities of research results and will last throughout the lifetime of the HUTER project. The first version was developed using the open-source framework HUGO and designed as a modern, static, and modular website which allowed visitors to navigate through the main areas of interest through tabs (Home, Work Packages, Participants, News and Contact). The second version (Fig. 4) of the HUTER website launched in September 2020 includes additionally a unique access point for all HUTER digital solutions, such as HUTER data platform, intranet, electronic case report form (eCRF), etc. To ensure privacy and security of data, all HUTER users have exclusive personal credentials to access to this private area that links with all HUTER digital solutions. The HUTER website is hosted on AWS server and it is managed by INCLIVA and BAHIA to ensure that it will remain online, updated, and accessible during the entire project period. Each partner can upload their contributions or messages by contacting INCLIVA or BAHIA.

Human Uterus Cell Atlas

The HUTER project aims to create the single-cell and spatial reference map of the human uterus. HUTER project will provide unprecedented insight at transcriptomic, genomic and spatial changes of this important female organ not only throughout the menstrual cycle but also across lifespan.

2 Years of duration
2020 - 2021

6 International partners

4 Countries

4.2M European funding (M€)

ABOUT HUTER PROJECT

The human uterus is a major female reproductive organ essential to the continuity of the human species, and also plays an important role on infant and maternal mortality and morbidity and women's health.

HUTER is the first project that focus on the transcriptomic, genomic and spatial changes of the uterus at single cell level throughout the menstrual cycle and across lifespan. The gained knowledge will contribute to better understand the human uterus and move forward its clinical translation in reproductive medicine, obstetrics, gynecology and regenerative medicine.

Prof. Carlos Simón, Project Coordinator

Figure 4. HUTER webpage update in September 2020

Since HUTER website is focused above all on general public, an accessible but professional language is used as well as impacting images and visual appeal, therefore the importance of the last update performed by BAHIA.

Internal communication between partners is facilitated with the **HUTER intranet platform** (Fig. 5). Documents and files for management and C&D such as templates, deliverables, procedures, guides for C&D, and documents related to the C&D activities undertaken (press release, publications, photos from events, etc.) can be uploaded on this project collaborative space created with limited access to partners. So that, all partners are fully informed about planning and work in progress.

Figure 5. HUTER access to the intranet for internal communication between partners purposes.

Internal communication is also achieved through partners participation in internal meetings, both face-to-face and online.

- **Kick-off meeting in Valencia, January 9th and 10th 2020:** In this first project meeting, HUTER consortium defined the activities that were to be developed during the first six months and established the required collaboration framework between partners (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Photograph of the HUTER kick-off meeting.

Since March 2020 all internal meetings has taken place on a virtual way on the frequency shown in Table 3 provided:

COMMITTEES	LEADER	DUE	DATES MEETING HELD
Steering Committee SC	Dr. Carlos Simón	Every 6 Months	December 9 th -10 th 2020 May 29 th 2020 December 10 th 2020
Ethical Management Committee EMC	Dr. Andres Salumets	Months 12 and 24 of the project	December 15 th 2020
Scientific & Technical Committee STC	Dr. Roser Vento-Tormo	Every 3 months	July 2 nd 2020 October 2 nd 2020 December 8 th 2020
Innovation Committee IC	Dr. Sergio Figueiras	TelCo on high frequency	

Table 3. Internal Meeting schedule and meetings held during the first year

JOINT LANDING PAGE FOR ATLAS PROJECTS

According to recommendations of European Commission (EC), we have been collaborating with other Atlas Projects (Braintime, Discovair, Espace, HCA organoid and Hugodeca) to create a joint landing page in the Human Cell Atlas global website for all European Atlas Projects (www.humancellatlas.org/euh2020/) (Fig. 7). The joint landing page allows HCA global website visitors (www.humancellatlas.org/) to connect and access directly to HUTER project website (and also to other Atlas Projects) which improves visibility and impact of our project activities globally. The development of this page was coordinated by partner LINQ of ESPACE project. HUTER is present through the reproduction network (Prof. Roser Vento-Tormo and Prof. Cecilia Lindskog) <https://www.humancellatlas.org/areas-of-impact/>. In addition, LINQ shared with all Atlas projects a document titled “H2020-HCA Cluster Social Media Strategy”, the document provides the social media strategy framework for joint communication efforts through the cluster projects’ social media accounts. It is designed to provide guidance and resources that make it easier for the H2020-HCA cluster to disseminate information about the cluster across social media and to support each other’s communication activities. See Annex VII.

Figure 7. Joint landing page for the 6 European atlas projects.

SOCIAL NETWORKS:

Twitter and Instagram (Instagram not much used) accounts were created right at the start of the project to further disseminate the latest news about the HUTER project or HCA initiative, retweeting from HCA account (<https://twitter.com/humancellatlas>) has been performed and participation in events, the *HCA Virtual Meeting HCA_EC consortia update meeting (is prove of that)* and 7 Virtual Seminars related to the HCA initiative.

Partners continue being encouraged and informed about the importance of the C&D actions, therefore to tag the project (@HUTER_HCA) when used. LinkedIn was taken as main point for communication actions as it proves to be very professional. The highest article visualized counted with 434 visits (see Figure 8).

The accounts used are:

- Twitter: @Huter_HCA
- Instagram: @Huter_HCA

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/huterproject/>

Figure 8. Example of LinkedIn visualization

Use of social media contributes to public engagement with the project. BAHIA and INCLIVA partners are managing these accounts, but other partners are encourage to contribute to their content.

PRESS RELEASES:

A press release was launched after the HUTER kick off meeting, to communicate the project’s aims and objectives and introducing the consortium to society (see Annex III) in the different local languages of partner’s countries. A good impact in written and digital press was obtained in the following days. Some examples: <https://bit.ly/3rT3KEJ>; <https://bit.ly/3qm2wSl> ; <https://bit.ly/3pjE4PV>; <https://bit.ly/2ZhAOtZ>; <https://incliva.es/newsletter-incliva-febrero-2020>. The press release was published within 17 media (written and on-line).

Another press release will be disseminated at the end of the project to highlight the project’s results and recommendations.

BROCHURE & VIDEO:

A brochure and video aimed at informing the general public about HUTER project and its expected impacts is ready to be released previous approval by the Steering Committee, it will be used during second year of the project, when is expected to most actively participate in events and for the workshop scheduled in month 22 (which may be delay on time as per extension of six months requested to the EC).

HUTER CONSULTATIONS:

Besides the two SMEs in the HUTER consortium (BAHIA and CCHT), we have involved enterprises (SMEs and large companies) as Industrial Advisory Board Members.

The Industrial Advisory Board (IAB) was set up after the formal invitation letters sent were accepted. The first meeting to present the project took place on December 10th 2020 by the HUTER project coordinator Prof. Carlos Simon where all the partners were present following the Steering Committee previously held.

The IAB is formed by 8 industry experts from companies related to IT and Biotechnology, for confidential clauses its names will just be provided only upon request by the European Commission. The IAB members are supporting the project in the definition of use cases for industry which are helping us to think about the inclusion of new features, approaches and functionalities in the HUTER platform. Their advice is helping us to gain knowledge on the industries interests that will build a bridge aiming to foster their take up after the project. 6 out of the 8 questionnaires sent has already been answered.

The design of the online questionnaire has facilitated the work. Respondents had direct and easy access to the questions and the results are easily obtained and exploited by the HUTER team. The pdf version of the questionnaire has been also elaborated in a way that is shared by direct email communication (see questionnaire in annex IV).

Our aim continues on creating a private network which could invest resources in subsequent stages of development. HUTER workshop (described below) will serve as well for this purpose.

Therefore with the creation of the IAB we have initiated industry consultations to get feedback from a variety of stakeholders that might be interested in the technologies and tools that will be developed in the framework of the HUTER project. This feedback could help us to get a real understanding of user needs as well as to improve some of the proposed platform features. Their vision, preferences could also be an asset to better address future user needs and to accelerate the impact of cell sequencing technologies and related ICT technologies in the market and particularly in the healthcare sector.

Accordingly, HUTER consultations will take us closer to the market landscape and it will serve us to improve the adaptability, usability and exploitability of the future HUTER Platform to other scenarios beyond the uterus and reproductive medicine field and sectors, such as the pharma and drug development industry, the medical device-diagnostic industry, the clinical trials industry, and particularly the healthcare sector as a whole.

HUTER WORKSHOP:

HUTER workshop is scheduled in month 22. Approximately 50 researchers (including PhD students) from academic institutions and technological enterprises will be invited. The objective of the workshop is to raise awareness of the Uterus Cell Atlas as essential resource for further research and developments, and to disseminate its results and to get first-hand feedback on their initial impressions on usefulness, usability, intended use and main difficulties in their early learning curve.

HUTER workshop falls as well into the category of **exploitation channel** since it will serve to recognize stakeholders that can “make use of the results”.

HUTER workshop may be delay as we are in the process of requesting an amendment mainly due to Covid-19 closed down on biopsies to be performed within hospital and samples shipment.

REPORTS AND OTHER PROJECT DOCUMENTS:

A total of 24 public deliverables will be issued within HUTER framework. These deliverables contribute to communicate and disseminate HUTER project and its results.

1.5.2 Other C&D channels

To maximize our communication and disseminate objectives in a targeted manner, we are making use of already available and effective dissemination channels and/or platforms such as:

PARTNERS AND COLLABORATORS WEBS:

Besides the HUTER official website and social networks that plays a key role in communication and dissemination activities, the HUTER partners and external collaborators which are directly or indirectly involved in the project have created a link from their websites to the HUTER’s one (<https://igp.uu.se/research/hpa/>; <https://incliva.es/investigacion/proyectos-destacados>; <https://ventolab.org/news/>; <https://bahiasoftware.es/innovacion-bahia-software>; <https://bahiasoftware.es/innovacion-bahia-software>). These linkages will further increase visibility among the external targeted audiences as well as dissemination of the results among international scientific community. Our initial analysis of external collaborators leads us to explore linkages with the following websites:

The Human Cell Atlas (www.humancellatlas.org): the global Human Cell Atlas initiative harbours a joint landing page (www.humancellatlas.org/euh2020/) which links with HUTER website and other Atlas Projects. This tight collaboration with the HCA initiative facilitates to maximise visibility as well as the expected impact in a wider population.

The Human Protein Atlas (<https://www.proteinatlas.org/>): one of our partners (UPPSALA) is actively involved in The Human Protein Atlas initiative. This initiative aims to map of all human proteins in cells and tissues by integrating results from various technologies, such as advanced microscopy images, sharing a similar concept to Human Cell Atlas Initiative. HUTER project can collaborate with its own protein images of uterus cells to Protein Atlas thus both websites could be linked to share and disseminate these data.

This linkage will be performed later as soon as there is any data added to the HUTER website, but as there is currently no generated data, we have not done this. There is also a possibility to not only link the databases, but perhaps also import the protein data generated via HUTER to show the actual data also on the Human Protein Atlas. This will be discuss when we have the data and can compare the quality of the data.

Furthermore, Human Protein Atlas is already a well-known initiative among scientific community (started on 2003) whose linkage to HUTER might give us more visibility among external audiences.

SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS AND PARTICIPATION IN SECTOR CONFERENCES AND MEETINGS:

All partners should disclose the project results in peer-reviewed scientific publications, ensuring open access¹ (free of charge online access for any user) either by publishing in an open access journal (gold open access) or by self-archiving their journal articles in an open access repository (green open access), and deposit the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications. Main journals in the field are Nature, Human Reproduction, Stem Cells, J. Clin Endocrinol Metab, Fertility & Sterility, etc.

Most HUTER partners are members of medical and scientific associations such as European Society of Human Reproduction and Embryology (ESHRE); American Society for Reproductive Medicine (ASRM); Society for Reproductive Investigation (SRI), International Society for Stem Cell Research (ISSCR), Preimplantation Genetics Diagnosis International Society (PGDIS). Once we have results from the samples within the project, partners will disseminate their results by taking advantage to their participation in such associations and their events for disseminate the HUTER project itself and its results. At the start of the project we commented on in the possible conferences and events in the field of Human Reproduction that we could target (ASRM October 2020 in Oregon (USA), ESHRE: July 2020 in Copenhagen, SRI, in Vancouver March 2020). Due to COVID-19 this has to be postponed as results are not ready yet. Participation is also planned in Conferences on Single Cell characterization technologies, and frontier research in cellular biology. Also conferences and events on use of Open Clouds in Science, computational advancements and bioinformatics. This will be reviewed in 2021.

¹ Jeffery, Keith G. 2006. "Open Access: An Introduction". Ercim News, 64, January 2006.

To what HUTER partners, mainly WP leaders, have been encouraged to participate in **coordination meetings with the HCA and other Atlas projects (EC-H2020 Consortia: Pilot actions to build the foundations of a human cell atlas)**. As commented previously, all consortia attended to the *HCA Virtual Meeting HCA_EC consortia update meeting* on September 22nd 2020, where Project Coordinator and WP Leaders introduce the project to the rest of the Atlas projects and updated on the tasks that were being performed. This mechanism ensures coherence and communication between both HCA and projects funded under this topic. The EC organized the overall coordination between projects. In this respect, HUTER partners also participated at the start of the project in:

- **European HCA networking meeting in Brussels, January 13rd and 14th 2020:** it was a network meeting between all European Atlas Projects partners and EC. Each project coordinator was able to share a presentation of his Atlas Project to foster discussion about potential synergies in relevant aspects, such as communication and ethical approaches, among Atlas Projects partners. Furthermore, this meeting was opened to external stakeholders and technology experts to analyze the potential technology transfer between Atlas Projects' results and other markets, particularly in healthcare sector (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. Photograph of the Project Coordinator Prof. Carlos Simón presenting HUTER project, during the HCA networking meeting in Brussels, Jan 13th 2020.

Table 4 provides a summary of attendance by HUTER partners during year 2020.

Day	Month	Year	Title	Format	Type
27	8	2020	HCA Developmental Stem Cell, Organoid Models, and Regenerative Biology Session	Virtual Seminar	Attendace
22	9	2020	HCA Virtual Meeting HCA-EC consortia update meeting	Virtual Seminar	Project Coordinator presenting the HUTER Project. Presentation of the latest developments of the six funded EC-HCA projects.
24	9	2020	HCA Latin America Workshop	Virtual Seminar	Project Coordinator participation as Speaker
25	9	2020	HCA Latin America Workshop	Virtual Seminar	Project Coordinator participation as Speaker
1	10	2020	HCA COVID-19 Virtual Symposium	Virtual Symposium	Attendance
9	10	2020	HCA COVID-19 Virtual Symposium	Virtual Symposium	Attendance
27	10	2020	HCA Developmental Neurons Seminars Europe	Virtual Seminar	Attendance
8	12	2020	HCA Developmental Clinical & Rare Disease Seminar	Virtual Seminar	Attendance

Table 4. Attendance to events and virtual meetings

OPEN ACCESS RESPOSITORIES:

As highlighted on deliverable D8.1 and D9.2 besides publishing our results and findings in high impact open-access journals, we will also deposit research data needed to validate results submitted in scientific publications after the project ends. These data will be gathered in open-access repositories following article 29 rules and in compliance with GDPR law. This open data deposit will not only guarantee the validation of published results by scientific community but will also ensure dissemination and exploitation of these data that could contribute to achieving new findings beyond HUTER project context.

Human Cell Atlas Data Coordination Platform (HCA DCP) will be the main repository of HUTER data after the project ends. HCA DCP is an open source, cloud-based platform developed to organize, standardize, and make accessible the data that constitute the Human Cell Atlas. All relevant data considered by HUTER partners will be transferred from HUTER platform to HCA DCP. This will guarantee the data persistence once the project ends and it will also allow external users to find and download these data. BAHIA team as WP Leader of WP2 and WP7 are working very close with the HCA making sure that data integration is achieved in a smooth way.

Apart from using HCA DCP we plan to also use other open repositories for different data types. ELIXIR (intergovernmental organization that brings together life science resources from across Europe) offers other European open-data repositories for different data types, settling a data sharing support for H2020 pilot projects. We are planning the use of:

- Array Express (EMBL-EBI): is one of the repositories recommended by major scientific journals to archive functional genomics data from microarray and sequencing platforms to support reproducible research. For high-throughput sequencing based experiments the raw data is brokered to the European Nucleotide Archive, while the experiment descriptions and processed data are archived in ArrayExpress.

- Single Cell Expression Atlas (EMBL-EBI): is an open science resource that gives users a powerful way to find information about gene and protein expression. It provides freely available information on the abundance and localization of RNA (and proteins) across species and biological conditions such as different tissues, cell types, developmental stages and diseases among others. Datasets are manually curated, re-processed and loaded into this resource, adding the value of testing for data quality.
- HPA: it contains information for a large majority of all human protein-coding genes regarding the expression and localization of the corresponding proteins based on both RNA and protein data.
- SpatialDB: a database for spatially resolved transcriptomes. SpatialDB is the first public database that specifically curates spatially resolved transcriptomic data from published papers, aiming to provide a comprehensive and accurate resource of spatial gene expression profiles in tissues. Currently, SpatialDB contains detailed information of datasets generated by 8 spatially resolved transcriptomic techniques (Spatial Transcriptomics, Slide-seq, LCM-seq, seqFISH, MERFISH, Liver single cell zonation, Geo-seq and Tomo-seq).

The list of open repositories will be further discussed in deliverable focused on data management D9.3.

NEWSLETTERS:

A specific HUTER newsletter was created <https://incliva.es/newsletter-incliva-febrero-2020> and there is also a section dedicated to the latest news from the project in its website <https://huter-hca.eu/news/#>. Furthermore, partner institutions inform about the developments of the project:

INCLIVA: <https://bit.ly/3rT3KEJ>; <https://bit.ly/3qm2wSI>; <https://bit.ly/3pjE4PV>; <https://bit.ly/3pjE4PV>;
<https://bit.ly/2ZhAOtZ>;

UPPSALA: <https://uu.se/nyheter/artikel/?id=14014&typ=artikel>

BAHIA: <https://bahiasoftware.es/web/innovacion-bahia-software.php?var1=&var2=&var3=&rewrite=&pagina=1>

PUBLIC AUTHORITIES EVENTS:

In order to better reach policymakers target audience, it is recommended to participate in events at any regional, national or European level organized by public authorities in the field of healthcare and national medical systems.

As an example, the HUTER coordinator participated in a health event in the Valencian region of Spain (Fig. 10), where HUTER was recognized as a project with a gender perspective

(<https://www.incliva.es/actualidad/noticias/incliva-acoge-la-iv-jornada-de-investigacion-sanitaria-con-perspectiva-de-genero>):

Figure 10. Prof. Carlos Simón (HUTER project coordinator) receives the recognition of “project with gender perspective” for HUTER project, in the ‘IV Conference on clinical research with a gender perspective’ organized by the Conselleria de Sanitat Universal i Salut Pública.

1.6 Procedures and management

1.6.1. Responsibilities

All partners of the HUTER consortium must contribute to the communication and dissemination according to their foreseen role and effort and using all available tools and channels described before.

As leaders of the WP8, representatives of INCLIVA and BAHIA as stated in Table 5 are in charge of Dissemination and Communications activities. The Communication and Dissemination Manager (C&D-M) is the central contact point for all partners to address C&D issues.

Table 5. Detailed information about the internal contact points for communication and dissemination issues related to HUTER project.

Partner short name	Role	Responsibilities	Appointed person*	Contact info
INCLIVA	Project Coordinator	Review content of draft academic publications, press releases and others	Dr. Carlos Simón	Carlos.simon@uv.es
	Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Manager	Main contact point to centralise all C&D issues	Eugenia Flores	eflores@incliva.es
	Science Communication (Comunicación Científica) Área Científica	Manage press releases and social media tools	Marta Ballester Collado	mballester@incliva.es

BAHIA	Innovation Project Manager	Manage general HUTER website and HCA landing page	Dr. Cristóbal Bernardo-Castiñeira	cristobal.bernardo@bahiasoftware.es
	Innovation Manager	Launch and manage industry consultations. Lead and constitute the IAB	Sergio Figueiras	sergio.figueiras@bahiasoftware.es

**Note: With the exception of the HUTER coordinator, the listed persons here may be replaced by others due to internal restructuring needs of the entities.*

1.6.2. HUTER C&D policies and rules

All HUTER partners follow the general policies and rules with respect to communication and dissemination activities they undergo:

- Dissemination of results governed by procedure of Article 29.1 of the GA: “Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium)”.

- Dissemination of own results: as stated in article 8.4.2 of the CA, during the project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the HUTER project, the dissemination of own Results by one or several Parties including but not restricted to publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 29.1 of the Grant Agreement subject to the following provisions. Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least **45 calendar days** before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within **30 calendar days** after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

- Dissemination of another partner’s unpublished results or background: (Art. 8.4.3 of the CA) a partner shall not include in any own dissemination activity another partner’s results or background without obtaining **partner’s prior written approval**, unless they are already published.

- Articled 29.2 and 29.3 of GA regarding the open access: Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results” and “Regarding the digital research data generated in the action (‘data’), the beneficiaries must: (a) deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user; (b) provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves)”. Therefore, the consortium partners will abide by these rules in relation to project results.

-Article 39: obligation to protect personal data: The beneficiaries must process personal data under the Agreement in compliance with applicable EU and national law on data protection.

- Funding publicity: All publications must mention that the project has received funding from EU using the EU emblem and the information and disclaimer text:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 874867.

- Cooperation obligations: as agreed in the CA (art. 8.4.4), partners undertake to cooperate to allow the timely submission examination, publication and defense of any dissertation or thesis for a degree that includes their results or background subject to the confidentiality and publication provisions agreed.

1.6.3. HUTER C&D procedures

Use of logos and templates: all partners should follow and use the HUTER brand guideline and templates created and deposited in the HUTER intranet → Diss&Comm folder → templates folder. However, for the use of the name of the partners or any of their logos or trademarks it is required the written approval as stated in the CA (art 8.4.5).

Report to the C&D Manager and upload files to the common repository: All partners shall communicate to the C&D Manager their dissemination and communication activities and upload the material on the HUTER intranet (papers, conference presentation, an audio file of an interview, etc.).

For all dissemination activities: notify all partners minimum 45 days prior to publication submission date or a presentation on a conference. Other parties have 30 days to object. The general overview for dissemination procedure is provided in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Dissemination procedure

Academic publications: All draft articles must be sent to the consortium partners involved in obtaining the results that are going to be disseminated and to the Project Coordinator and C&D Manager before publication for reporting and archiving purposes. This will allow checking if they fulfil the dissemination requirements or whether they conflict with other existing papers.

Congress contributions: partner or partners who intent to make congress contributions, should send the material to the C&D Manager in order to ensure homogenous identity.

Press release protocol: several press releases are expected to be launched at least at the beginning and at the end of HUTER project. The draft content can be prepared by any partner or in collaboration by several of them but final draft should be centralised by the C&D Manager who will send to all partner and the project Coordinator for revision and final approval before publication. Each partner will be responsible for translation to its local languages.

Personal photographs of people: protection of personal rights is important. Thus all consortium members are required to ask for the consent of people they wish to take photographs of all the time at all events during the

course of the project. A consent form template is provided in Annex V to use during the HUTER workshop and other occasions.

1.7 Evaluation

1.7.1. Reporting

For monitoring purposes, we agreed that the communication and dissemination activities were to be reported every 6 or 8 months to the C&D-M. In the end, we requested an update to partners in September 2020. This information is provided on the first year Periodic Technical Report.

Table 6 planned at the start of the project for gathering information was not used, instead the template within the participant portal was used to facilitate the compilation of information (Table 6.1).

Table 6. Data to be reported regarding communication and other dissemination activities

Partner	Name of the activity	Dates of the activity	Country of the activity	Target group	Kind of material used	Link of the material	KPIs reached
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Table 6.1. Updated document for data gathering on communication and other dissemination activities

Specify the number of Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the project for each of the following categories	Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of all dissemination and communication activities
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)
Exhibition	Industry
Flyer	Civil Society
Training	General Public
Social Media	Policy Makers
Website	Media
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	Investors
Participation to a Conference	Customers
Participation to a Workshop	Other
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	

Video/Film
Brokerage Event
Pitch Event
Trade Fair
Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)
Other

For the **scientific publications** we will continue as planned and will be reported as on Table 7:

Table 7. Data to be reported regarding scientific publications

Scientific publications	Choose one or insert
Type of scientific publication	Article in journal
	Publication in conference proceeding/workshop
	Number of pages visited per session
	Books/monographs
	Chapters in books
	Thesis/dissertation
Title of the scientific publication	
DOI reference	
ISSN or Essn number	
Authors	
Title of the journal or equivalent	
Number, date	
Publisher	
Place of publication	
Year of publication	

Relevant pages	
Public & private publication	YES
	NO
Peer-review	YES
	NO
Is/Will open access provided to this publication	YES – Green OA
	YES – Gold OA
	NO

The compiled information will be reported in due time on deliverable *D8.4_Record on the Dissemination, Exploitation and IPR* and during the Final Report to be delivered to the EC as scheduled in Table 8.

Table 8. Scheduled periodic reports

Report	Period covered	Template ready and uploaded to intranet by C&D-M.	Deadline to send to Project Coordinator.	By whom?	Finalised & submitted to EC.
Periodic Report 1	Jan 2020 - Dec 2020 (M01 – M12)	Dec 2020 (M12)	Jan 2021 (M13)	All partners	Feb 2021
Periodic Report 2	Jan 2021 - Dec 2021 (M13 – M24)	Dec 2021 (M24)	Jan 2022 (M25)	All partners	Feb 2022

1.7.2. Metrics and key performance indicators (KPIs)

For the purposes of measure the progress and impact of HUTER communication and dissemination activities, quantitative/qualitative indicators as initial KPIs have been identify (Table 9). This Table will be updated following HUTER requirements in the next report in order to be more accurate towards reality.

Table 9. The main communication channels/tools that are going to be used in communication and dissemination plan and the ways to measure their impact.

Communication tool/channel	KPI	Results Year 2020
Website	Number of users	484
	Number of visits	5107
	Number of pages visited per session	2.73
	Number of sessions through external URLs	307
Press releases	Number of media that have published the press releases	17
Social Media:	Number of followers	Twitter HUTER: 40 followers LinkedIn HUTER: 93 followers INCLIVA Twitter Followers: 4,470

		INCLIVA LinkedIn Followers: 8,262 INCLIVA Facebook Followers: 5,776
	Number of impressions	Twitter HUTER: 28.8K impressions
	Number of clicks/interactions	Twitter HUTER: 814 interactions
Brochure	Number of brochures distributed	
Video	Number of visualizations on YouTube	
Per-review Publications	Number of submitted scientific papers	1
	Number of articles accepted	
	Impact Factor of the journals (average and accumulated)	
	Number of citations	
	Views	
	Downloads	
Attendance of conferences or professional events	Number of attended conferences with presentations of posters	
	Number of attended congresses - oral communications	
HUTER consultations	Number of questionnaires sent	8
	Number of completed questionnaires collected	6
	Number of questionnaires collected per sector	2 IT sector / 4 biotechnology sector
HUTER workshop	Number of registered people in the workshop	
	Number of external audiences attending	
	Type of external audience attending (by target groups)	

To inform that, INCLIVA written press has got a total of 1.824 appearances of which 136 are in printed press and its audience reaches 28.167.796 users.

In addition to the KPI, a 1 radio interview took place, and partners have participated in 5 conferences: Lorne Proteomics Symposium, Lorne, Australia; Scandinavian Translational Pathology Seminar, Bergen, Norway; UK

HCA meeting; Wiezmann Institute single-cell conference; Wellcome trust single-cell biology conference. Also, participation in 1 workshop Earlham Institute single-cell symposium.

We have calculated that apart from INCLIVA as coordinator we have reached: Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research) over 16000, Industry over 1000, General Public 1.833.174, Policy Makers, Media and Investors over 500.

2 EXPLOITATION

By signing the GA (Art. 28) the partners agreed to “take measures to ensure exploitation of the results (either directly or indirectly, in particular through transfer or licensing) up to four years after the end of the project – by using them in further research activities; developing, creating or marketing a product or process; creating and providing a service, or using them in standardization activities.

Therefore, **exploitation** recognizes own partners and stakeholders that can “make use of the results” and “concretize the value and impact of the R&D activity. Datasets, HUTER platform architecture, standards software and results business cases fall into this category.

To better understand, it is important to remember that **results** are defined as “any tangible or intangible output of the action (project), such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected”.

It is important to highlight here that participation in Open Access.

In this sense and in accordance with the requirements of Grant Agreement – Art. 28, we have established the strategy in the HUTER project framework, to promote the major benefits from the results obtained.

2.1 Objectives and strategy

This exploitation plan aims to primarily approach to the project exploitation by representing an initial exploitation strategy that will be enforced during the project lifetime, enable an actual impact on future research and applications to human reproduction and women’s health, thanks to the utilization of some of HUTER results for the development of products or services that will benefit patients and physicians.

Specific objectives of the exploitation plan are:

1. To define a strategy to **identify which HUTER results are suitable for exploitation**
2. To **pave the way for** a successful commercial and non-commercial **exploitation** of the project outcomes, buy:

- definition of a valorisation plan.

- to engage stakeholders in order to maximize target market awareness through dissemination and exploitation activities such as, journals and participation in conferences, organization of the HUTER workshop and the Industry Advisory Board (IAB).

The HUTER exploitation plan enables an actual impact on future research and applications to human reproduction and women's health, thanks to the utilization of some of HUTER results for the development of products or services that will benefit patients and physicians.

2.2 Exploitation activities

Some activities used for exploitation purposes are already covered in the Dissemination section such as project website, press releases, HUTER workshop, Industry consultations (HUTER questionnaires), scientific papers and participation in conferences. All these activities are mainly used to increase awareness and engage main stakeholders that can make use of the project results. Additionally, the use of standard or common laboratory procedures and methods between partners and collaborators such as HCA will facilitate the exploitation of results.

Other specific exploitation activities are described below:

2.2.1. Identification of exploitation results

Before disclosing any result, partners must assess their potential for exploitation and/or protection (see fig. 11). This evaluation will be carried out by the Innovation Committee (see section 2.3.1.) starting from the information reported by partners in the Results Evaluation Form (Annex VI). Final revision will be taken by the Steering Committee with the partners involved in the results, and decisions about protection and dissemination will be taken.

2.2.2. Industry Advisory Board (IAB)

Steps has been taken and key stakeholders are involved in the HUTER project by means of the IAB, which is a non-executive body constituted by representatives of innovative biotech, genetic, clinics and IT companies (both SMEs and large enterprises), interested in the HUTER platform.

Industry representatives have been carefully selected and asked to complete the HUTER questionnaire (Industry consultations – Annex IV). Initially planned for month 6, but achieved in month 12. The IAB representatives were invited to become part of the IAB by the Innovation Committee and finally approved by the Steering Committee. The IAB members are also invited to participate in some consortium meetings as

experts in technology and as scientific advisors and in business cases activities or/and HUTER workshop when organized. A separate non-disclosure agreement (NDA) is in process of signature between HUTER partners and each IAB member.

2.2.3. Promotion

For highly exploitable results identified, the route for carrying out further exploitation will be outlined. It will include the type of intellectual property strategy, further activities and investments needed to reach the market or potential end users and the potential partners who will be in charge of its exploitation. The owner (or co-owners when it applies) is responsible for drafting the valorisation plan.

It will be strongly recommended to first promote the results to be exploited among the industrial members of the HUTER consortium (BAHIA and CCHT partners), always that these results are related to the market sectors where these companies operate.

The owner will be the first responsible for the implementation of promotion actions regarding its results and using its own resources.

Regarding the protection of results, the owner will follow its internal rules and procedures according to its national intellectual property law. Where possible, a patent application will be filed in first term at the European Patent Office, using the national patent office of the European applicant filing office. Additionally, in case of joint ownership, co-owners shall agree the corresponding joint ownership agreement according to article 8.2 of the HUTER CA where it is strongly recommended to appoint one representative for negotiations with third parties.

2.3 Exploitation Management

2.3.1. Innovation Committee (IC)

According to the governance of the HUTER consortium, whereas the Steering Committee (ST) is responsible for the overall coordination of the project and it represents the last step in the decision-making process, the coordination of the activities related to the IPR management and the exploitation of the R&D results will be under responsibility of the Innovation Committee (IC).

Dr. Sergio Figueiras (BAHIA) as Innovation Manager (IM) will lead the partners in effective management of the project innovations working closely with the other IC representative appointed by each partner/beneficiary. The IC assumes the role of Innovation Management in the project, managing the identification

and implementation of the innovations, and the feedback linkages to the research. It will evaluate the knowledge as it is generated in line with its market impacts and ensure that the project results are effectively protected and exploited to the full for future industrial growth and competitiveness. The IC will also ensure that the data management plan is seamlessly executed and decide on all matters related to IPR and exploitation, IPR protection mechanisms, IPR sharing and routes to exploitation, and project Dissemination Plan and Business Plan. IC will also act as a driver for defining post-project exploitation strategy, both in the framework of the global HCA initiative and the engagement of additional actors, especially with SMEs and industry representatives, acting also as main connection with the IAB members for future sustainability and exploitation matters.

2.3.2 Update on HUTER Exploitation management activities

1) The impact of COVID19 pandemic in HUTER Exploitation Management activities:

HUTER exploitation management activities have been severely impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. The crisis and the laboratory lockdowns across Europe have significantly reduced the number of samples and the possibility to execute of some of the projected experiments. Several experiments have been evolving at lower pace during the first months of the projects and as an immediate consequence, the potential R&D results expected from those experiments are also suffering a delay. In these circumstances, the difficulties experimented in the R&D labs have obviously impacted the initial innovation dissemination strategies.

2) Executed activities related to HUTER Exploitation Management activities:

- Despite the unfavourable circumstances for the obtention, dissemination and exploitation of R&D results, we have experienced some progress in this important project field. The main progress is related to the negotiation and final signature of the HUMAN CELL ATLAS INITIATIVE (HCA) COLLABORATION AGREEMENT agreed with the other six European projects funded by the Pilot Actions Human Cell Atlas Initiative of the Horizon 2020 program. During the discussion meetings, several representatives of the HUTER IC participated in the discussions and agreed important clauses related to the exploitation of potential R&D results in accordance with the expectations of the project partners, the Horizon 2020 policies, and the general precepts of the Human Cell Atlas Initiative for the exploitation of R&D results.
- The creation of the Industrial Advisory Board was another important step of the Innovation strategy of the HUTER project. First IAB activities have initially been oriented to the exploitation of the HUTER software platform but it could be later extended to other potential R&D results from other partners.

In fact, the HUTER consortium already decided a set of activities with the IAB to identify and ideally guide promising R&D results in their route to the market.

3) Next steps of the HUTER IC:

The HUTER IC expects a more intense activity in the second half of the project. As the HUTER R&D activities progress, we expect R&D findings that could require careful analysis and customized activities to facilitate its technology transfer to the market. Among the different activities for the second half of the HUTER project, we consider the following:

- Increasing the alignment of the IC with the IAB: The HUTER IAB is formed by high level representatives from the industry and entrepreneurs with proven experience in the development of health technologies. They know very well the challenges related to the transformation of R&D results into commercially and financially viable products. In the incoming months we will try to take as much advantages as possible from the IAB, organizing meetings to present and evaluate promising R&D results from the different HUTER partners.
- Periodic IC meetings: For the second half of the project, the HUTER-IC will have periodical meetings to identify R&D results with enough potential to reach the market and to revise the IPR policies already agreed in the HUTER Consortium Agreement and with other initiatives very much related with HUTER such as the Human Cell Atlas Initiative and the other six European projects funded by the “Pilot Actions Human Cell Atlas Initiative of the Horizon 2020 Program”.
- As the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic is reduced, we would like to increase dissemination activities (through the participation in virtual and face-to-face meetings) that could contribute to the innovation strategy of the HUTER project.

2.3.3. Exploitation rules and procedures

Identification of exploitable/protectable results: any results will be reviewed by the Innovation Committee before being disclosed. Accordingly, any planned publication will be notified to all partners at least **45 calendar days** before the publication as mentioned in section 2.5.2.

Internal disclosure of results: Any deliverable generated during the project with a dissemination level classified as “Confidential” according to the list of deliverables of HUTER (GA number 874867 — Annex 1 (part A) section 1.3.2. WT2 list of deliverables) will be reported to the Steering Committee for revision and approval before submitting.

- Article 26 of the GA and Article 8 of the Consortium Agreement (CA) regarding ownership of results and intellectual property (IP) rights protection: results are owned by the partner that generates them of, if generated by a third party, the partner on whose behalf such results have been generate. Joint ownership is governed by GA article 26.2 with the following additions:

- Where Results are generated from work carried out jointly by two or more Parties and where their respective contribution to the joint Results cannot be ascertained or it is not possible to separate such joint Results for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining the relevant intellectual property rights protection, they shall have joint ownership of those Results.
- Following the generation of a joint Result, the joint owners shall agree, in a joint ownership agreement, on (i) the allocation of ownership, (ii) the protection measures to be taken, (iii) the division of related costs and (iv) the Exploitation of such jointly owned Result.
- However, until a joint ownership agreement has been concluded:
 - a. Results shall be jointly owned according to their share of contribution (such share to be determined by taking into account in particular, but not limited to, the contribution of a joint owner to an inventive step, the person months or costs spent on the respective work, etc.) to the Results by the joint owners concerned.
 - b. Except for any priority application(s), in the event that any of the Results may be protected as registered intellectual and/or industrial property rights or by any other means, the Parties shall decide by mutual agreement to implement/apply for such protection in the manner they deem most convenient.
 - c. All costs related to application(s) for Intellectual Property Rights, or other means of protection, in joint Results and the Intellectual Property Rights resulting from such application(s)/protection shall be shared between the joint owners in accordance with their share of contribution

- d. Each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned Results for non-commercial research activities, including publicly funded projects, on a royalty free-basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owners, and each of the joint owners shall be entitled to otherwise Exploit the jointly owned Results and to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties (without any right to sub-license), if the other joint owners are given:
 - (a) at least 45 calendar days advance notice; and
 - (b) Fair and Reasonable compensation

- Article 30 of the GA and Article 8.3 of the CA about transfer of Results:

- Each partner may transfer ownership of its own Results following the procedures of the Grant Agreement Article 30.
- It may identify specific third parties it intends to transfer the ownership of its own Results and the other partners waive their right to prior notice and their right to object to a transfer to listed third parties according to the Grant Agreement Article 30.1.
- The transferring partner shall, however, at the time of the transfer, inform the other partners of such transfer and shall ensure that the rights of the other partners will not be affected by such transfer.
- The partners recognize that in the framework of a merger or an acquisition of an important part of its assets, it may be impossible under applicable EU and national laws on mergers and acquisitions for a partner to give the full 45 calendar days prior notice for the transfer as foreseen in the Grant Agreement.
- The obligations above apply only for as long as other partners still have - or still may request - Access Rights to the Results.
- In case a partner that jointly owns Results with another, wishes to transfer its share of the jointly owned Results, it shall first give 45 calendar days prior notice to the other joint owners as foreseen in the Grant Agreement and shall, in any case, at the time of the transfer, inform the other Parties of such transfer and shall ensure that the rights of the other Parties will not be affected by such transfer

-Article 9 of the CA refers to access rights and identification of the background for the project identified by the partners, and where relevant, informed each other that access rights to specific background is subject to legal restrictions or limits.

2.4 Evaluation / Promotion

Although quantity and quality of peer-reviewed publications, presentations at international conferences, data and methods are the most important outputs in terms of dissemination and scientific impact, the project should not be evaluated using bibliometric and academic methods only, but also using indicators like “reports or white papers, forecasts, workshops, business cases, etc.”

ANNEXES

I. HUTER Brand Guideline

BRAND FOR HUTER
HOW TO USE IT CORRECTLY

SYMBOL COLOUR

SYMBOL AND LOGO COLOUR

SYMBOL BLACK

SYMBOL AND LOGO BLACK

TYPOGRAPHY LOGO

<p>ARIAL BOLD</p> <p>ASBCDEFGHIJKL MNOPQRSTUW WXYZ abcdefghijklmn opqrstuvwxyz 0123456789</p>	<p>ARIAL BOLD ITALIC</p> <p>ASBCDEFGHIJKL MNOPQRSTUW WXYZ abcdefghijklmn opqrstuvwxyz 0123456789</p>
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<p>PRIMARY COLOUR</p> <p>#2478BB</p>	
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II. HUTER templates

Deliverable cover page:

Project Acronym:	HUTER				
Project Full Name:	Human Uterus Cell Atlas				
Call Identifier:	H2020-SC1-2019-Single-Stage-RTD				
Topic:	SC1-BHC-31-2019				
Grant Agreement No:	874867				
Start date of Project:	01/01/2020				
Project Duration	2 years				
Document due date:	xx/xx/202X				
Submission Date	Xx/xx/202x				
Leader of this report:	XXXXX				
Deliverable no:	XX.X				
Deliverable name:	XXXXX				
Contact name:	xxx				
Dissemination level:	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)				
Version History					
Version	Date	Details			
1.0	Xx/xx/202x	XXXXXXXXXXXX			
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 874867.					
The opinions expressed in this document reflect only the author's view and in no way reflect the European Commission's opinions. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.					

PowerPoint template:

III. HUTER Kick-off meeting Press release (original language)

NOTA DE PRENSA

INCLIVA impulsa el proyecto HUTER, financiado por la Unión Europea, con el objetivo de crear el mapa celular del útero humano

HUTER, dirigido por el profesor Carlos Simón, surge de la necesidad de mejorar el conocimiento del útero humano para aumentar la eficacia de los tratamientos de reproducción asistida y evitar la mortalidad y la morbilidad materna e infantil

Valencia, 14 de enero de 2020. El Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria INCLIVA, del Hospital Clínico de Valencia, ha impulsado el proyecto internacional HUTER (Human Uterus Cell Atlas), que tiene como objetivo crear el mapa celular del útero humano para proporcionar una visión sin precedentes, célula a célula, de los cambios genéticos y proteómicos, a nivel espacial, de este importante órgano, no solo durante el ciclo menstrual sino también a lo largo de toda la vida de la mujer.

Las investigaciones en las que se centran este proyecto, coordinado por INCLIVA y que dirige el profesor Carlos Simón –Catedrático de la Universidad de Valencia e Investigador Principal del Área de Medicina Reproductiva de INCLIVA y Fundación Igenomix- parte de la consideración del útero humano como un órgano fundamental no solo para la reproducción, ya que es donde se va a gestar el nuevo ser, sino también por sus implicaciones en la salud de la propia mujer y de sus hijos.

HUTER se enmarca en la iniciativa internacional Human Cell Atlas (HCA), integrada por investigadores de todo el mundo que pretenden redefinir la anatomía humana a nivel de célula única en todos los órganos vitales del cuerpo humano.

HUTER es el único proyecto que trabajará en el útero de la mujer para aumentar su conocimiento y traslación clínica en medicina reproductiva, obstetricia, ginecología y medicina regenerativa. El útero es en sí mismo un modelo en medicina regenerativa, ya que el tejido endometrial se regenera mensualmente y su transformación se ejecuta a través de cambios dinámicos e interacciones de múltiples tipos celulares.

En este sentido, la principal motivación de HUTER surge de la necesidad de comprender mejor el útero humano para abordar de manera más efectiva las enfermedades uterinas que afectan a la salud de la mujer, como los miomas o la

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Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria

endometriosis, y pueden contribuir a la infertilidad, la mortalidad y la morbilidad materna e infantil.

INCLIVA es la entidad coordinadora de este proyecto, financiado por la Unión Europea, en coordinación con Wellcome Sanger Institute (UK), uno de los centros genómicos líderes en el mundo, que colabora activamente con la iniciativa HCA; Uppsala University (Suecia), una institución internacionalmente destacada y una de las sedes de la iniciativa Human Protein Atlas, iniciada en 2003 con el objetivo de mapear todas las proteínas humanas en células, tejidos y órganos; Competence Centre on Health Technologies (Estonia), una mediana empresa establecida en 2009, que realiza investigaciones de alto nivel orientadas al cliente y desarrolla productos y tecnologías principalmente para la medicina reproductiva y fetal; University of East Anglia (UK), clasificada en el puesto 15 por The Times Good University Guide 2019; y Bahía Software (España), una empresa de tecnología fundada en 1999 y especializada en el sector de la salud, cuyo catálogo de servicios y productos cubre todo el ciclo de vida del desarrollo de software y consultoría en tecnologías específicas.

HUTER, cuya reunión de inicio tuvo lugar en la sede de INCLIVA los pasados días 9 y 10 de enero, es un proyecto que tiene un horizonte temporal de dos años (2020 y 2021). Está financiado por el programa H2020 de la Comisión Europea, con un total de 4,118 millones de euros.

Este es el segundo proyecto internacional de INCLIVA, que también coordina LEGACy, un proyecto internacional y multicéntrico -liderado por el Dr. Andrés Cervantes, director de INCLIVA y coordinador del Grupo de Investigación en Cáncer Colorrectal y Nuevos Desarrollos Terapéuticos en Tumores Sólidos, y la Dra. Tania Fleitas, investigadora Joan Rodés del grupo mencionado-, que tiene como objetivo mejorar el abordaje del cáncer gástrico aplicando la medicina personalizada.

Below is shown the press clip on January 15th, reflecting the impact in the media of the press release:

The screenshot shows a digital archive interface for INCLIVA. At the top, there are logos for 'EL PAÍS', 'LA NARRATIVA', 'Extensión', 'ABC', and 'El Periódico'. Below these is a calendar for January 2020, with the 15th highlighted. The main content area displays a list of news items:

- 56 INCLIVA** (Impreso, Digital)
 - 3 Impreso**
 - LAS PROVINCIAS** Las Provincias
 - El Clínico impulsa el mapa celular del útero humano**
R. V. VALENCIA. El Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria INCLIVA, del Hospital Clínico, impulsa el proyecto Internacional HUTER (Human Uterus Cell Atlas). Su objetivo, crear el mapa celular del útero para proporcionar una visión célula a célula de los cambios genéticos y proteómicos de este órgano a lo largo de la vida de la mujer. Las investigaciones, dirigidas por el catedrático Carlos Simón y financiadas por la UE, parten de...
 - LAS PROVINCIAS** Las Provincias
 - La AECC beca cinco trabajos contra el cáncer**
... Estas líneas de investigación se desarrollarán en tres centros valencianos de referencia: la Fundación para la Investigación del Hospital La Fe de la Comunitat Valenciana, la Fundación para la Investigación del Hospital Clínico de Valencia y el ...
 - LAS PROVINCIAS** Las Provincias
 - El Soro recibe el alta tras su hospitalización por sufrir repetidas anginas de pecho**
J. L. B. VALENCIA. El torero valenciano Vicente Rùiz 'B Soro' recibió ayer el alta tras pasar casi una semana ingresando en el Hospital Clínico de Valencia por una recaída de su enfermedad cardíaca. Tras sufrir, mientras dormía, un fuerte dolor en el pecho el pasado miércoles y no remitir con el tratamiento habitual, el SAMU le trasladó al hospital, donde ingresó de urgencia. El jueves los cirujanos cardiovasculares del equipo del doctor Bodi, le practicaron un cateterismo para evaluar daños y...
 - 3 Digital**
 - ABC** ABC
 - El INCLIVA impulsa un proyecto para crear el mapa celular del útero humano**
... e infantil, según un comunicado de la entidad científica. El proyecto está dirigido por Carlos Simón, catedrático de la Universitat de València (UV) e investigador principal del Área de Medicina Reproductiva de INCLIVA y Fundación Igenómik. El objetivo del proyecto HUTER (Human Uterus Cell Atlas) es crear el mapa celular del útero humano para proporcionar una visión sin precedentes, célula a célula, de los cambios genéticos y proteómicos, a nivel espacial, de este importante órgano, no solo durante el ciclo menstrual sino también a lo largo de toda la vida de la ...
 - 20 Minutos**
 - AECC Valencia beca a cinco jóvenes investigadores para avanzar frente al cáncer de mama, estómago, próstata e infante**
... de referencia en el ámbito de la Investigación oncológica: la Fundación para la Investigación del Hospital La Fe de la Comunidad Valenciana, la Fundación para la Investigación del Hospital Clínico de Valencia (Incliva) y el Instituto Valenciano de Oncología (IVO), detalla la organización en un comunicado. "Las becas doctorales que otorgamos son, sin duda, un estímulo para la ciencia, pero también son una oportunidad para dar salida al talento de los jóvenes en la fase predoctoral, un momento crítico en el que existe menos ayuda y financiación pública para continuar ...

IV. HUTER questionnaire

Display of the online form that will be launched to industry target group:

HUTER

The Human Uterus Cell Atlas

Industry Consultations

HUTER platform will be an integrative digital platform for molecular data, advanced images and research management of Human Uterus Cell Atlas project (huter-hca.eu). This questionnaire aims to get information from industry companies about functionalities and technical features which will be considered for HUTER platform design.

**Obligatorio*

Contact information

Company name *

Tu respuesta

Sector

Tu respuesta

Contact name *

The draft content of the questionnaire is shown below:

Industry Consultations

Company name:

Sector:

Contact name:

Email address:

Summary: HUTER platform will be an integrative digital platform for molecular data, advanced images and research management of Human Uterus Cell Atlas project (huter-hca.eu). This questionnaire aims to get information from industry companies about functionalities and technical features which will be considered for HUTER platform design.

Answer these questions on behalf of your company:

1. About Human Cell Atlas (<https://www.humancellatlas.org/>)
 - a) Do you know the Human Cell Atlas initiative? (yes/no)
 - b) Do you think that a common repository with cellular maps of all tissues could help to improve the understanding, diagnostic and treatment of diseases? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
 - c) Could an integrative platform of advanced images and OMICS data allow transfer this complex knowledge to industry sector and human health (clinical practice)? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
 - d) Among OMICS data, are you familiar with Single Cell Sequencing technologies and their potential to diagnose and understand diseases? (yes/no)
 2. About HUTER (huter-hca.eu):
 - a) Do you know HUTER (Human Uterus Cell Atlas project)? (yes/no)
 - b) Do you think that a common repository with cellular maps of all tissues could help to improve the understanding, diagnostic and treatment of diseases related to reproductive medicine? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
 3. Single cell sequencing technologies already enable researchers to perform a complete molecular characterization of tissues at the resolution of individual cells (<https://rdcu.be/b3nNY>).
- **By sectors:**
 - a. Do you think that these technologies will be relevant for human health sector soon?
 - High probably
 - Medium probably
 - Low probably
 - Never
 - Don't Know/No Answer
 - b. Do you think that these technologies will be relevant for pharma industry soon?

- High probably
 - Medium probably
 - Low probably
 - Never
 - Don't Know/No Answer
- c. Do you think that these technologies will be relevant for agricultural biotech industry soon?
- High probably
 - Medium probably
 - Low probably
 - Never
 - Don't Know/No Answer
- d. Do you think that these technologies will be relevant for animal biotech industry soon?
- High probably
 - Medium probably
 - Low probably
 - Never
 - Don't Know/No Answer
- By technology:
- e. Do you think that these technologies will be relevant for drug development soon?
- High probably
 - Medium probably
 - Low probably
 - Never
 - Don't Know/No Answer
- f. Do you think that these technologies will be relevant for medical device and diagnostic technologies soon?
- High probably
 - Medium probably
 - Low probably
 - Never
 - Don't Know/No Answer
4. Regarding cell sequencing technologies:
- a. What will be the most interesting molecular approaches in the next 1-5 years for the human health sector? (rate from 1 to 10)
- Single-cell sequencing (NGS)
 - Single-cell epigenomics
 - Single-cell RNAseq (transcriptomics)
 - Spatial/In Situ RNAseq (transcriptomics)
 - Spatial proteomics
 - Others (write)
 - None of them, this technology will not reach clinicians in that period
 - Don't Know/No Answer
- b. What will be the most interesting molecular approaches in the next 1-5 years for the pharma industry-drug development? (rate from 1 to 10)
- Single-cell sequencing (NGS)

- Single-cell epigenomics
 - Single-cell RNAseq (transcriptomics)
 - Spatial/In Situ RNAseq (transcriptomics)
 - Spatial proteomics
 - Others (write)
 - None of them, this technology will not reach pharma industry-drug development
 - Don't Know/No Answer
- c. What will be the most interesting molecular approaches in the next 1-5 years for the medical device and diagnostic technologies? (rate from 1 to 10)
- Single-cell sequencing (NGS)
 - Single-cell epigenomics
 - Single-cell RNAseq (transcriptomics)
 - Spatial/In Situ RNAseq (transcriptomics)
 - Spatial proteomics
 - Others (write)
 - None of them, this technology will not reach medical device and diagnostic technologies
 - Don't Know/No Answer
- d. What will be the most interesting molecular approaches in the next 1-5 years for the clinical trials industry? (rate from 1 to 10)
- Single-cell sequencing (NGS)
 - Single-cell epigenomics
 - Single-cell RNAseq (transcriptomics)
 - Spatial/In Situ RNAseq (transcriptomics)
 - Spatial proteomics
 - Others (write)
 - None of them, this technology will not reach clinical trials industry
 - Don't Know/No Answer
5. What is in your opinion the potential impact of digital platforms on hospitals and clinical practice that? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
- Analyze, exploit and visualize molecular (OMICS)
 - Analyze, exploit and visualize advanced microscopy images
6. What is in your opinion the potential impact of digital platforms on the pharma industry-drug development that? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
- Analyze, exploit and visualize molecular (OMICS) data
 - Analyze, exploit and visualize advanced microscopy images
7. What is in your opinion the potential impact of digital platforms on the medical device and diagnostic technologies that? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
- Analyze, exploit and visualize molecular (OMICS) data
 - Analyze, exploit and visualize advanced microscopy images
8. Do you think that digital platforms for analyzing, hosting and visualizing molecular data and advanced microscopy images will be prioritized in some clinical areas within the next 5 years? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
- Cardiology
 - Endocrinology

- Oncology
 - Pediatric diseases
 - Rare diseases
 - Reproductive medicine
 - Rheumatology
 - Urology
 - Others (specify)
9. What will be the most interesting cellular imaging generation techniques for human health sector in the next 1-5 years? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
- Spatial transcriptomics techniques based on probe hybridization and RNA-seq (such as 10x technologies and similar)
 - Spatial transcriptomics techniques based on multiplex in situ hybridization (such as smFISH, MERFISH, RNAScope and similar)
 - Proteomics techniques combined with immunofluorescence microscopy
 - Proteomics based on immunohistochemical methodologies (microtissue array, immunohistochemical whole slide and similar)
 - Others (specify)
10. What will be the most interesting cellular imaging generation techniques for pharma industry-drug development in the next 1-5 years? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
- Spatial transcriptomics techniques based on probe hybridization and RNA-seq (such as 10x technologies and similar)
 - Spatial transcriptomics techniques based on multiplex in situ hybridization (such as smFISH, MERFISH, RNAScope and similar)
 - Proteomics techniques combined with immunofluorescence microscopy
 - Proteomics based on immunohistochemical methodologies (microtissue array, immunohistochemical whole slide and similar)
 - Others (specify)
11. What will be the most interesting cellular imaging generation techniques for medical device and diagnostic technologies in the next 1-5 years? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
- Spatial transcriptomics techniques based on probe hybridization and RNA-seq (such as 10x technologies and similar)
 - Spatial transcriptomics techniques based on multiplex in situ hybridization (such as smFISH, MERFISH, RNAScope and similar)
 - Proteomics techniques combined with immunofluorescence microscopy
 - Proteomics based on immunohistochemical methodologies (microtissue array, immunohistochemical whole slide and similar)
 - Others (specify)
12. What will be the most interesting cellular imaging generation techniques for clinical trials industry in the next 1-5 years? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
- Spatial transcriptomics techniques based on probe hybridization and RNA-seq (such as 10x technologies and similar)
 - Spatial transcriptomics techniques based on multiplex in situ hybridization (such as smFISH, MERFISH, RNAScope and similar)
 - Proteomics techniques combined with immunofluorescence microscopy

- Proteomics based on immunohistochemical methodologies (microtissue array, immunohistochemical whole slide and similar)
 - Others (specify)
13. Do you think that digital platforms for single cell technologies and in particular those platforms that serve to analyze, exploit and visualize molecular data and advanced microscopy images could be useful for clinical trials of advanced therapies (such as immunotherapy or gene therapy)? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
14. International Standards and open formats in digital platforms could facilitate the integration of collaborative functionalities due to the use of common file formats. Do you think that standard formats for molecular and imaging data will be necessary to facilitate the adoption by clinicians? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
15. Do you think that algorithms which automatically transform data from private formats from single-cell equipment manufacturers to open international standards would be useful in this platform? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
16. Do you know the following standards? (yes/no/No Answer)
- DICOM® (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine)
 - HL7 standard (Health Level Seven)
 - SNOMED (Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine)
 - LOINC (Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes)
 - CDA (Clinical Document Architecture)
 - CCR (Continuity of Care Record)
 - GELLO
 - GEM (Guideline Elements Model)
17. Do you consider DICOM as the optimal international standard to transmit, store, retrieve, print, process, and display medical imaging information? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
18. Would be DICOM a good standard to deploy and implement new advanced research microscopy images in clinical practice? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
19. If not, could you specify other formats which could be good candidates to be standards for new advanced research images? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
- BIGTIFF
 - MRXS
 - SWS
 - NDPI
 - OMETIFF
 - BMP
 - JPG
 - TIFF
 - Others (specify)

20. Do you think that other tools used by researchers in the field of microscopy (OMERO, Bioformats, etc) have the potential to reach hospitals, pharma industry, at a global scale? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
21. Which of these applications related with imaging field should be integrated in a digital platform that will serve both researchers and clinicians? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
- ImageJ
 - OMERO
 - Others (specify)
22. Do you know portals to analyze, exploit and visualize OMICS data from research databases? Please, write the name of the portal or the website.
23. What of these portals related with OMICS data should be integrated in a digital platform that will serve both researchers and clinicians? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
- Single Cell expression atlas (EBI-EMBL)
 - Single Cell Portal (Broad Institute)
 - Terra
 - UCSC Xena Single Cell Browser
 - Others (specify)
24. Do you think that these analysis tools could help clinicians during their daily clinical practice? (yes/no or Don't Know/No Answer)
25. Do you think that automatic algorithms which perform analyses on images would be useful in this platform? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
- Interest regions identification
 - Cell counting
 - Customized macros
 - Others (specify)
26. Would be useful to interchange molecular and image data (e.g. from rare diseases) to receive feedback using standards such as DICOM and HL7 between clinical and research sectors? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
27. Molecular data results obtained by advanced molecular techniques can have descriptive associated metadata. Do you think that standardized terminology for molecular metadata (like SNOMED in medical field) could be exploited by big data, AI and other technologies? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
28. Would be useful online co-collaborative work capabilities on advanced images with tele-diagnostic purposes (such as co-diagnostics between several professionals from different centers)? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)
29. EU patient's data are considered private data that must be have restricted access to compliance with GDPR law. Which importance do you give to the security/data privacy protocols that must be

implemented in digital platforms that manage Omics data and advance microscopy images from patients? (rate from 1 to 10 or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)

30. Under your point of view, what of the following features would be interesting for HUTER platform? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)

- Management tools
- Chat
- Videoconference
- Advanced visualization tools
- Online co-working functionalities
- Electronic case report format
- Genomic visor
- Transcriptomic visor
- Command line interface
- User-friendly web interface
- High-throughput data analysis online
- Conversion algorithms (to standard formats)
- Synchronized data store
- Dynamic storage
- Special transfer protocols for heavy file
- Compatible with third-party portals via APIs
- Export/import data tools
- Virtual reality tools
- Others (specify)

31. Do you think that digital platforms solution that integrate OMICS data and advanced microscopy images should be integrated in Laboratory Information Systems (LIS)? (rate from 1 to 10, or rate 0 for Don't Know/No Answer)

- From Research labs (genomics, epigenomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, etc.)
- From Hospital departments (Anatomy Pathology, Genomic services, Radiology unit, etc.)

V. “Consent Form” – template for using personal photographs of project participants for project purposes.

Consent form

Yes, I want to be informed about the HUTER project

Name:

Address:

Phone:

E-mail:

Consent:

I hereby declare my consent that personal data including video and pictures taken during the HUTER project workshop/event may be processed and stored by the HUTER consortium for the organization and execution of the research project HUTER, particularly for communication purposes to a wider public. Pictures/videos may appear on HUTER website, consortium partners websites, social media and similar media. HUTER consortium will not use the data for any other purpose. This consent may be revoked at any time by contacting at contac@huter-hca.eu.

Signature

Date

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 874867.

VI. Results Evaluation Form

RESULTS EVALUATION FORM

Objective: To classify the results from HUTER according to their potential for exploitation, avoiding the disclosure of those suitable to be protected before its dissemination or exploitation.

The following form should be filled by the partner/s that generates the result and reviewed by the Innovation Committee and finally approved by the Steering Committee. Results should remain confidential (out of public disclosure) until the approval by the Steering Committee.

TITLE (TENTATIVE) OF THE RESULT

SHORT DESCRIPTION

(Type of result: new product (good or service), new method, new process, software, etc.)

THE RESULT HAS BEEN PUBLICLY DISCLOSED (YES / NO)

WHAT AREA OR FIELD OF APPLICATION IS IT DIRECTED TO?

HUTER PARTNER/S WHO HAS OBTAINED THE RESULT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 874867.

OTHER CONSORTIUM MEMBERS WHO HAVE CONTRIBUTE TO THE RESULT

OTHER THIRD PARTIES WHO HAVE CONTRIBUTE TO THE RESULT

FIELD OF APPLICATION, MARKET OPPORTUNITY AND TIME TO MARKET

RESULT STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT (TRL) AND JUSTIFY

NOVELTY

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 874867.

RESULT STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT (TRL) AND JUSTIFY**TYPE OF IP RIGHTS IF PROTECTION IS POSSIBLE**

(Patent, Trademark, registered design, utility model, other)

FIRST APPROACH TO EXPLOITATION**ADDITIONAL COMMENTS (if needed)**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 874867.

VII. H2020-HCA Cluster Social Media Strategy

H2020-HCA Cluster Social Media Strategy

Authors: Anna-Lena Guske (LINQ), Claudia Schacht (LINQ), Erika Granath (LINQ), Samantha Wynne (Wellcome Sanger Institute), Tracey Andrew (Wellcome Sanger Institute)

 These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements No. 871626, 871655, 874703, 871710, 871711, and 871827.

VIII. Web traffic HUTER Website

Analytics The Human Uterus Cell Atlas project
Todos los datos de sitios ...

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Audience Overview

All Users
100.00% Users

1 Jan 2020 - 31 Dec 2020

Overview

■ New Visitor ■ Returning Visitor

Language	Users	% Users
1. es-es	166	33.74%
2. en-us	152	30.89%
3. es	58	11.79%
4. zh-cn	43	8.74%
5. en-gb	24	4.88%
6. de	11	2.24%
7. fr-fr	7	1.42%
8. en	6	1.22%
9. sv-se	3	0.61%
10. es-419	2	0.41%